

SPEECH THERAPIST PERSONNEL IN PREPARATION PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES DEVELOPMENT ORGANIZATIONAL AND METHODOLOGICAL DIRECTIONS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the organizational and methodological directions of developing professional competencies in the process of training speech therapists. The study covers the issues of increasing the effectiveness of speech therapy education, the formation of professional skills and competencies of future specialists through the use of practical training and innovative pedagogical technologies. The article also shows the role of interactive methods, game technologies and corrective exercises in the educational process, as well as their importance in developing speech, diagnostic and pedagogical skills of future speech therapists.*

Keywords: *speech therapist training, professional competence, organizational and methodological directions, speech therapy education, pedagogical technologies, innovative methods, practical exercises, interactive methods, game technologies, speech development, correctional pedagogy, pedagogical skills, diagnostics, special education, professional qualifications.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, reforms aimed at introducing innovative approaches to the training of high-quality personnel in the field of special pedagogy are being systematically carried out. The formation of the academic and social trajectory of students in higher education based on competency-based approaches is bearing fruit. This requires improving the content of higher education based on advanced foreign trends, targeted and intensive introduction of information and communication technologies into the pedagogical process, and effective methods for developing professional competencies in students through integrative training. In particular, analyzing the hours corresponding to specialization modules in higher education curricula, selecting the sequence of topics in the context of integration, and preparing control tasks for modules in a complementary manner allow students to prepare for professional activity early.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

In the process of studying scientific sources within the framework of the study, we found that integrative training is an important factor in the training of speech therapists, in particular, in the development of their professional competence. In this regard, there is a need to interpret the interpretations of concepts such as professional competence and professional skills. We found that professional competence is given various interpretations and definitions in scientific sources and is studied in different structures. Below are some definitions, descriptions and approaches:

VI Andreev lists the following components that make up competence: "A person's positive motivation, knowledge, skills, talents and experience of creative activity in the field, as well as an integral indicator, a developing level of preparation, manifested in solving educational, professional and other complex problems"[22]. We believe that according to the components listed

by the scientist, it is possible to distinguish the components of the professional competence of future speech therapists.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

The organizational and methodological importance of developing professional competencies in the process of training speech therapists is very great. It makes it possible to make the educational process systematic, effective and sustainable, to combine the theoretical knowledge of future specialists with practical skills. Through organizational and methodological approaches, speech therapists are trained not only to identify speech disorders and conduct corrective work, but also to develop pedagogical and communicative skills.

Also, these areas allow for the integration of innovative and interactive methods into the educational process, the formation of creative and reflexive thinking of future specialists through practical exercises and game technologies. The organizational and methodological significance is that it serves to improve the quality of speech therapy training, ensure methodological stability, and train competent speech therapists who are ready for professional activity. As a result, we have explained the professional competence of future speech therapists by dividing them into components as follows:

Axiological . This competence requires the formation of the following skills and qualifications in speech therapists: establishing professional relationships, forming a professional worldview, analyzing the causes of communicative problems encountered in practice, understanding the individuality of the speech therapist (himself) and the child and self-awareness, predicting the achievement of the goal set, having professional ethics, knowing one's profession as a value, recognizing the principles of humanity as a rule, etc.

Socio-legal. This competence requires the formation of the following professional knowledge, skills and qualifications in speech therapists: knowledge of the essence of regulatory and legal documents on occupational safety, special, inclusive education, compliance with the rules and standards of technical safety, protection of children, adolescents and adults with speech disorders from negative external and internal factors (affecting their lives and well-being) in the correctional and pedagogical process, taking measures to prevent such problems, formalizing the work carried out, searching for, finding and applying effective ways to find extrabudgetary funds, etc.

Correctional-pedagogical, methodological. This competence requires the formation of the following professional knowledge, skills and qualifications in future speech therapists: understanding the importance of creating a creative environment in the organization of correctional-pedagogical work, studying various modern approaches to self-development, applying innovations found effective among them in practice, drawing up and developing a training plan; regular work on oneself, effective organization of the activities of children with speech defects in classroom and extracurricular activities, application of various modern methods and means of correction, compensation, knowledge of the principles and essence of person-oriented education, their use in the pedagogical process, readiness to perform various tasks in educational institutions, use of psychological mechanisms and their alternative forms; educational and corrective influence on the general and speech development of children, etc.

Communicative: This competence requires the formation of the following social skills and competencies in future speech therapists: organizing interactive activities, working in cooperation, being tolerant, choosing effective strategies and tactics in professional and life problem situations, active participation in the team, providing defectological and practical

assistance to the socialization of children with speech disorders, self-management, assessment, development and the ability to visualize the results of scientific-methodological, scientific-pedagogical activities, etc.

The professional competence of a future speech therapist is the basis for his successful work, effective work with patients, application of new methods and professional growth. Therefore, in the process of speech therapy education, great attention should be paid to the development of not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills.

CONCLUSION

The component we have chosen actually embodies the professional skills that should be formed in all professional fields. Therefore, among modern professions, the profession of speech therapist, which has its own comprehensive and integrative content, is based on knowledge of several disciplines. The issue of integrative development of knowledge of medicine, linguistics, psychology, pedagogy, neuropedagogy and other disciplines is considered a leading issue in the training of speech therapists. The professional competence of a future speech therapist is a key factor in the effective and high-quality implementation of his professional activities. This competence allows the specialist to identify speech disorders, properly organize diagnostic and rehabilitation work, apply an individual approach, use modern methods and technologies, and maintain ethical and professional relations with the patient. Also, professional competence serves the speech therapist's continuous professional development, improving his knowledge and skills, and ensuring confidence and security in his work. Therefore, the qualifications and knowledge of a future speech therapist are an important foundation for his future successful work.

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